

Exploring Metal Oxide Thin Film Structures to Enhance Charge Storage Capacity in Supercapacitors: Implications for Agricultural Innovation

Mbamara C^{1*}., Nworie C. I^{4,5}., Obodo R. M^{1,6}., Aniezi J. N¹., Ononogbo C²., Omugbe E¹., Brown-Okporie N. W⁴., Akande P.I⁷., Otah P. B^{4,5}., Ojobeagu A. O⁴., Amadi M. C³.

¹Department of Physics, University of Agriculture and Environmental Science, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Science, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

³Department of Biochemistry, University of Agriculture and Environmental Science, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Industrial and Medical Physics, David Umahi Federal University of Health Sciences (DUFUHS), Uburu Ebonyi State, Nigeria

⁵International Institute for Machine Learning, Robotics & Artificial Intelligence Research, (DUFUHS) Ebonyi State, Nigeria

⁶Department of physics and Astronomy, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, 410001, Enugu State, Nigeria

⁷Department of Industrial Physics, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: bookfashion9@gmail.com

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Abstract: In response to the increasing need for efficient energy storage, this study focuses on cobalt-doped nickel oxide (CoNiO) thin films as advanced materials for supercapacitors. These supercapacitors offer high power density, rapid charge-discharge cycles, and long-term stability, making them particularly useful in agricultural applications. Our research investigates the structural and optical properties of these films, aiming to boost their charge storage capacity for supercapacitor use and explore their potential for agricultural innovation. We synthesized the CoNiO thin films using a solution growth method. We prepared aqueous precursor solutions of 0.3 M and 0.5 M Nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate, each doped with 5% Cobalt (II) chloride. These solutions were used to deposit thin films onto glass substrates immersed in a heated chemical bath at 80°C for one hour. After deposition, we annealed the films at 373 K, 423 K, and 473 K to examine how thermal treatment affects their properties. We characterized the films structurally and optically using UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). XRD results confirmed the formation of a stable CoNiO phase, marked by a prominent diffraction peak at 31.0°, corresponding to the (220) crystal plane. SEM images revealed a significant transformation: unannealed films had smooth, amorphous surfaces, while annealed samples developed well-defined, polycrystalline nanostructures, indicating improved surface morphology and crystallinity. Optical analysis showed that annealing dramatically enhanced both absorbance and optical conductivity. The 0.3 M CoNiO film annealed at 473 K displayed optimal properties, including the highest conductivity and a tunable bandgap, making it highly suitable for efficient charge storage. Systematically adjusting precursor concentration and annealing temperature enhances CoNiO thin film performance, making them ideal for supercapacitors in off-grid, solar-powered smart farming applications.

Keywords: Annealing, bandgap, energy storage, agricultural innovation, smart farming.

Introduction

In recent years, the demand for efficient, high-performance energy storage devices has intensified, especially in sectors like agriculture that are increasingly reliant on smart technologies. From wireless soil sensors to automated irrigation systems, modern agricultural innovations require energy storage solutions that offer rapid charge–discharge cycles, long lifespan, and structural stability in diverse environmental conditions (Gür, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2018; Njema *et al.*, 2024). Supercapacitors, with their high-power density, excellent reversibility, and prolonged cycle life, have emerged ideal candidates to support such applications (Jiang *et al.*, 2015; Zhao *et al.*, 2017; Libich *et al.*, 2018; Olabi *et al.*, 2022). However, to meet the growing energy demands of remote and precision agriculture, it is essential to enhance the charge storage capacity of these devices through improved electrode materials. Transition metal oxides, particularly nickel oxide (NiO) (Zheng *et al.*, 2009; Kate *et al.*, 2018), have been widely investigated as potential electrode materials for supercapacitors due to their environmental friendliness, chemical stability, and pseudocapacitive properties. NiO is a wide bandgap p-type semiconductor known for its

good ion storage capacity (Das *et al.*, 2014; Ezeh *et al.*, 2023), making it suitable for energy storage and electrochromic applications. However, its practical performance is often hindered by relatively low electrical conductivity and limited active surface area (Sun *et al.*, 2011). To overcome these limitations, doping NiO with transition metals such as cobalt (Co) has been shown to be an effective strategy to tune its structural, optical, and electrochemical properties.

Cobalt-doped nickel oxide (Co-NiO) combines the beneficial redox activity of both Ni²⁺/Ni³⁺ and Co²⁺/Co³⁺ oxidation states, leading to enhanced electrical conductivity, increased density of active sites, and improved energy storage behavior. Additionally, Co doping can significantly influence the morphology and crystallinity of NiO thin films, further improving their pseudocapacitive performance. Studies have shown that binary Co-Ni oxides not only exhibit excellent capacitive characteristics but also possess multifunctional properties (Long *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2015), such as electromagnetic (EM) wave absorption and optical transparency, which are highly desirable for integrating supercapacitors into agricultural environments exposed to EM

interference from 5G and internet of things (IoT) devices.

In this study, cobalt-doped nickel oxide ($\text{Co}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{O}$) thin films were synthesized using the chemical bath deposition (CBD) method, an economical and scalable technique suitable for producing uniform coatings over large areas (Christian *et al.*, 2022; Nworie *et al.*, 2024). Films were grown at two doping concentrations (0.3 M and 0.5 M Co) and subsequently annealed at low temperatures (373 K, 423 K, and 473 K) to optimize phase formation, microstructure, and conductivity without damaging temperature-sensitive substrates. Characterization techniques such as UV–Visible spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were employed to study the optical bandgap, crystal structure, and surface morphology of the films.

The goal of this research is to explore how Co doping and annealing conditions affect the microstructural and optical properties of NiO thin films, and how these changes influence their suitability for use in supercapacitor electrodes. The central hypothesis is that Co incorporation will enhance redox activity, improve charge transfer, and increase the surface area available for electrochemical reactions, thereby boosting the overall charge

storage capacity of the material. Tailoring cobalt-doped NiO thin films for superior energy storage performance, this research aims to contribute to the development of durable, high-performance supercapacitors for agricultural technologies. These thin films can be integrated into energy-autonomous sensors, low-power electronics, and transparent energy-storing devices for greenhouses and field equipment. Furthermore, the potential for dual-functionality in electromagnetic shielding positions Co-NiO films as promising materials for use in the next generation of smart, sustainable, and resilient agricultural systems.

Materials and Methods

Aqueous solutions of 0.3 M and 0.5 M Nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were prepared. For doping, 5% molar concentrations of Cobalt (II) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were added. For 0.3 M CoNiO preparation: 7.13 g of Nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate and 0.36 g of Cobalt (II) chloride hexahydrate were dissolved in a 100 mL beaker. For 0.5 M CoNiO preparation: 11.88 g of Nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate and 0.60 g of Cobalt (II) chloride hexahydrate were dissolved in a 100 mL beaker. The mixed precursor solutions were complexed with 10 mL of ammonia (~25%), and the pH

was adjusted to 9 using 0.1 M NaOH (0.4 g of NaOH in 100ml).Thoroughly cleaned glass slides were vertically immersed in a 250 mL solution bath housing the precursor. The 250 mL beaker containing the precursor and slides was then placed in a 1000 mL temperature bath and heated at 80°C for one hour. After deposition, the slides were rinsed with distilled water, air-dried, and annealed at 373 K, 423 K, and 473 K for 1 hour. The solution growth, cobalt-doped Nickel oxide thin films were characterized using UV-Vis, X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) at the Nano/Advanced Physics Lab, University of Nigeria Nsukka. The absorbance data at (200-1000nm) were used to calculate all the optical and solid-state properties.

Results and Discussion

Optical characterization

Figures 1-2 shows the absorbance curve of the deposited films. The optical characterization of the cobalt-doped nickel oxide (CoNiO) thin

films reveals that absorbance was highest in the wavelength range of 350–450 nm for both 0.3 M and 0.5 M concentrations, with absorbance generally decreasing as wavelength increased. This agrees with the result of (Oh *et al.*, 2010; Das *et al.*, 2014; Nworie *et al.*, 2024). Annealing the films significantly influenced their optical behavior. For the 0.3 M films, annealing at 473 K resulted in the highest absorbance (0.35), compared to 0.28 at 373 K, 0.17 at 423 K, and 0.24 in the unannealed sample. Similarly, for the 0.5 M films, absorbance increased from 0.10 in the unannealed sample to 0.28 after annealing at 473 K, indicating that annealing improves the optical density and possibly the electronic structure of the films. However, increasing the concentration from 0.3 M to 0.5 M generally led to a reduction in absorbance, suggesting that higher precursor concentration might introduce optical scattering or structural defects due to agglomeration or excess thickness

Figure 1 Abs vs. λ for annealed and un-annealed 0.3 M CoNiO films.

These findings suggest that optimal annealing temperature (especially 473 K) enhances film crystallinity and charge transport properties, which are critical for energy storage in

Figure 3 Opt.Con vs. λ for annealed and un-annealed 0.3 M CoNiO films.

Figures 3 and 4 present the optical conductivity spectra for cobalt-doped nickel oxide (CoNiO) thin films at 0.3 M and 0.5 M concentrations, both in annealed and unannealed states. Across both concentrations, the highest optical conductivity was observed in the wavelength range of 354 nm to 450 nm, with conductivity values decreasing as the wavelength increased similar to that obtained by (Ishiwu *et al.*, 2024). This trend is

Figure 2 Abs vs. λ for annealed and un-annealed 0.5 M CoNiO films.

supercapacitors. Improved absorbance and structural properties make annealed 0.3 M CoNiO film ideal for supercapacitors.

Figure 4 Opt.Con vs. λ for annealed and un-annealed 0.5 M CoNiO films.

characteristic of semiconducting behavior, where photon energy is more effectively absorbed at shorter wavelengths, leading to increased charge carrier activity (Zhang *et al.*, 2016). For the 0.3 M CoNiO films, the optical conductivity varied with annealing temperature. At 373 K, the conductivity was approximately -58.2×10^6 S/m, at 423 K it decreased to about -60.2×10^6 S/m, while at 473 K, it slightly improved to -56.3×10^6 S/m.

The unannealed film had a conductivity of around -59.2×10^6 S/m. These variations suggest that annealing has a significant effect on the electronic structure of the films, with 473 K appearing to offer improved conductivity compared to the other annealing temperatures.

For the 0.5 M films, a similar pattern was observed. The unannealed film had a

conductivity of -59.7×10^6 S/m. Upon annealing, conductivity values were -58.7×10^6 S/m at 373 K, -60.1×10^6 S/m at 423 K, and -58.4×10^6 S/m at 473 K. Although changes were not as pronounced as in the 0.3 M films, annealing still led to modest improvements in conductivity, particularly at 473 K.

Figure 5 Plots of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs (hv) at 0.3M

Figure 6 Plots of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs (hv) at 0.5M

Figures 5 and 6 show the optical bandgap energies of cobalt-doped nickel oxide (CoNiO) thin films deposited at different concentrations and subjected to various annealing temperatures. The bandgap values were determined using the Tauc relation:

$$(\alpha hv)^2 = B(hv - E_g) \quad 1$$

Where α is the absorption coefficient, hv is the photon energy, B is a constant, and E_g is the optical bandgap energy.

For the 0.3 M CoNiO films, the bandgap was 1.68 eV in the unannealed state. When annealed at 373 K, the bandgap slightly reduced to 1.60 eV, and further decreased to 1.38 eV at 423 K. This downward trend suggests improved film crystallinity and reduction in structural defects, which can enhance electrical conductivity. However, when annealed at 473 K, the bandgap increased sharply to 1.85 eV, likely due to structural reordering or increased oxidation, which introduces a more insulating character

to the film. In contrast, the 0.5 M CoNiO films exhibited a different pattern. The unannealed and 423 K-annealed films both had a bandgap of 1.50 eV. At 373 K, the bandgap increased slightly to 1.67 eV. However, a significant rise was observed at 473 K, where the bandgap reached 2.54 eV. This dramatic increase may be attributed to densification, reduced defect density, or possible phase transformation, all of which

can widen the energy gap and reduce the material's electrical conductivity.

Structural characterization

Figures 7a-8d shows the structural analysis of the films which was carried out using X-ray diffraction (XRD) method with range of 10° - 75° on a computer-controlled Philips pin 1500 X-ray diffractometer of Cu-ka wavelength (1.5408\AA).

Figure 7a XRD patterns of 0.3M CoNiO film Un-annealed

Figure 7b XRD patterns of 0.3M CoNiO film synthesized at 373K

Figure 7c XRD patterns of 0.3M CoNiO film synthesized at 423K

Figure 7d XRD patterns of 0.3M CoNiO film synthesized at 473K

Figures 7a–7d and 8a–8d present the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of 0.3 M and 0.5 M CoNiO thin film samples, both unannealed and thermally annealed at 373 K, 423 K, and 473 K, respectively. Across all samples, a prominent diffraction peak was consistently observed at 31.0° , which corresponds to the (220) crystal plane of the CoNiO phase. This indicates the presence of a well-defined

Figure 8a XRD patterns of 0.5M CoNiO film Un-annealed

Importantly, as the annealing temperature increased from approximately 283K to 302K and further to 343K, the crystalline phase remained largely unchanged. This thermal stability suggests that the structural integrity

crystalline structure. This result is in similar to that obtained by (lan *et al.*, 2020). The pronounced diffraction peak at 31.0° is different from that obtained by Das *et al.*, 2014.

Figure 8b XRD patterns of 0.5M CoNiO film synthesized at 373K

of the CoNiO films is maintained across a range of temperatures, making them suitable for use in environments where moderate temperature fluctuations are expected.

Figure 8c XRD patterns of 0.5M CoNiO film synthesized at 423K

Figure 8d XRD patterns of 0.5M CoNiO film synthesized at 473K

Such stability is particularly advantageous for agricultural applications, where energy storage materials may be exposed to varying field conditions. The retention of crystalline order under thermal treatment implies that these CoNiO films can offer consistent performance and durability when used in supercapacitors or energy devices integrated into smart farming systems.

Morphological characterization

Figures 9a-d and 10a-10d shows the morphological structures of the unannealed and annealed films of 0.3M and 0.5M CoNiO at different concentrations and annealing temperatures.

Figure 9a SEM image of Un-annealed of 0.3M Cobalt nickel oxide film

Figure 9b SEM image of 0.3M Cobalt nickel oxide film annealed at 373k

Figures 9a - d and 10a - d display the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images of the 0.3M and 0.5M cobalt-doped nickel oxide (CoNiO) thin films under investigation. Generally, the films exhibited clear surface

morphology with visible grain boundaries, indicating significant structural changes resulting from both cobalt doping and thermal annealing.

Figure 9c SEM image of 0.3M Cobalt nickel oxide film annealed at 423k

Figure 9d SEM image of 0.3M Cobalt nickel oxide film annealed at 473k

Figure 10a similar to 9a, which represents the unannealed film, revealed a relatively smooth and amorphous surface with the presence of pinholes.

Figure 10a SEM image of Un-annealed 0.5M Cobalt nickel oxide film

Figure 10b SEM image of 0.5M Cobalt nickel oxide film annealed at 373k

Figure 10c SEM image of 0.5M Cobalt nickel oxide film annealed at 423k

This appearance suggests the retention of organic residues and solvents from the deposition process, resulting in a less defined grain structure and poor crystallinity. The surface appeared smoother but inhomogeneous, likely due to the incomplete decomposition of precursors or the presence of residual binders. In contrast, Figures 10b to 10d like in 9b to 9d, corresponding to films annealed at 373 K, 423 K, and 473 K respectively, showed a noticeable transformation in surface morphology. The annealed films developed nanostructured

features with more uniform and smaller grains, especially at the lower annealing temperatures. As the temperature increased, mild grain growth was observed, along with signs of crack formation, indicating the onset of stress relief and crystallite reorganization. These films exhibited a more pronounced polycrystalline morphology, confirming the role of annealing in enhancing grain development and improving the overall microstructure. This is slightly different from that obtained by (Oh *et al.*, 2010).

Figure 10d SEM image of 0.5M Cobalt nickel oxide film annealed at 473k

The results clearly demonstrate that thermal annealing significantly enhances the optical and electronic properties of CoNiO thin films. Annealing improves crystallinity, reduces structural defects, and increases charge carrier mobility, as supported by both optical conductivity data and SEM analysis. The highest optical conductivity was observed at 473 K, suggesting that this temperature yields optimal structural ordering, which is vital for high-performance electronic applications such as supercapacitors. The SEM images further confirm this, showing a transition from a smooth, amorphous surface in the unannealed film to a well-defined, nanostructured, polycrystalline morphology after annealing. This transformation contributes to better charge storage and faster charge-discharge cycles, which are critical for supercapacitor efficiency. Among the tested samples, the annealed 0.3 M CoNiO film stood out for its superior absorbance, conductivity, and structural properties, making it especially suitable for supercapacitor applications. These characteristics are highly relevant to agricultural innovation, where energy-efficient and reliable storage solutions are needed to support smart farming technologies. Optimizing both annealing temperature and precursor concentration is essential, as moderate annealing (around 373 – 423 K)

leads to narrower, more favorable bandgaps for charge transport. In contrast, excessive annealing particularly at higher concentrations can result in wider bandgaps and reduced electrical performance.

Conclusion

This study explored the structural and optical modification of cobalt-doped nickel oxide (CoNiO) thin films synthesized via the solution growth method, with the aim of enhancing charge storage capacity for supercapacitor applications, particularly in the context of agricultural innovation. The results demonstrate that thermal annealing significantly influences the crystallinity, optical absorbance, conductivity, and morphology of the CoNiO films. The XRD patterns confirmed the formation of a stable CoNiO phase, with a pronounced peak at 31.0° corresponding to the (220) plane. SEM micrographs revealed a transition from smooth, amorphous surfaces in unannealed films to well-defined nanostructured and polycrystalline textures in annealed samples, with improved grain distribution and surface uniformity. Optical studies showed that annealing enhanced the absorbance and optical conductivity, particularly at 473 K (200°C), which exhibited the highest conductivity and bandgap modulation. The

0.3 M CoNiO film annealed at 473 K showed optimal characteristics, combining strong absorbance, narrow and tunable bandgap, and improved microstructural features, making it suitable for better supercapacitor performance, which can support renewable energy applications in agriculture, especially in precision agriculture, post-harvest systems, and smart farming.

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Disclosure of Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement:

The data used in this study are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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